

OPTIMIZATION OF DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF PAIN SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE

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Abstract. *The assessment of the clinical and neurological features of pain syndrome in patients with Parkinson's disease requires a comprehensive approach, as pain syndrome can be multifactorial and have different mechanisms of origin. It is important to consider both neurological and non-motor manifestations of the disease. One of the most frequently observed symptoms in Parkinson's disease is pain syndrome, which significantly reduces the quality of life for patients. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), one in five people worldwide experiences severe or moderate pain. One in three of them is unable to live independently, and about 65% of the population is socially isolated due to chronic pain, unable to carry out daily activities. Approximately 30-50% of patients with Parkinson's disease develop cognitive impairments. These changes may include issues with attention, memory, executive functions, and perception. Parkinson's disease is characterized by the disruption of dopaminergic activity, which can lead to deficits in both motor and cognitive spheres. Pain can exacerbate these changes, as the activation of pain pathways may compete with dopaminergic pathways responsible for cognitive processes. Chronic pain and depressive symptoms, which are often present in Parkinson's disease patients, may contribute to the worsening of cognitive functions. Depression itself can be a risk factor for cognitive decline.*

Keywords: *chronic pain, Parkinson's disease, non-motor symptoms.*

Introduction. Research Objective: To assess the clinical and neurological features of pain syndrome in patients with Parkinson's disease. The study involved 107 patients aged between 45 and 75 years. The research material included samples of scales such as UPDRS, NMS Quest, VAS, Mac-Gill, and DN4. In 38 (59.4%) patients with pain syndrome, pain was observed on the side where motor symptoms (hypokinesia and rigidity) were more pronounced during the disease, or on the side where motor symptoms were more severe. In 2 (3.1%) patients, pain was observed on the opposite side. In 9 (14.1%) patients, bilateral pain was observed. It was established that in 15 (23.4%) patients, pain appeared before the onset of the disease symptoms.

Table 1

Distribution of patients by disease stages depending on gender.

Clinical Forms	Stage	Men (abs., %)	Women (abs., %)	Total (abs., %)
Akinetic-rigid	1st	6 (15%)	3 (7.5%)	9 (22.5%)
	2nd	9 (22.5%)	5 (12.5%)	14 (35%)
	3rd	9 (22.5%)	8 (20%)	17 (42.5%)
Tremor	1st	4 (13.3%)	2 (6.7%)	6 (20%)
	2nd	7 (23.3%)	2 (6.7%)	9 (30%)

Clinical Forms	Stage	Men (abs., %)	Women (abs., %)	Total (abs., %)
	3rd	11 (36.7%)	4 (13.3%)	15 (50%)
Mixed	1st	6 (16.2%)	4 (10.8%)	10 (27%)
	2nd	10 (27%)	3 (8.1%)	13 (35.1%)
	3rd	7 (18.9%)	7 (18.9%)	14 (37.8%)

A total of 69 (64.4%) male patients were included, showing that men are more frequently diagnosed with Parkinson's disease than women in a ratio of 1.81:1. Among the clinical forms of the disease, the ratio of akinetic-rigid to mixed forms was almost equal (1.1:1).

Table 2

Neurological Symptoms Manifestation

Symptom	With PS(n=64)	Without PS (n=43)
Rest tremor	43 (67.19±5.87%)	37 (86.05±5.28%)
Hyposmia/anosmia	37 (57.81±6.17%)	33 (76.74±6.44%)
Hypomimia	53 (82.81±4.72%)	39 (87.3±2.76%)
Postural disorders	38 (59.38±6.14%)	34 (79.07±6.20%)
Pseudobulbar syndrome	9 (14.06±4.35%)	11 (25.58±6.65%)
Asymmetry of deep reflexes	37 (57.81±6.17%)	26 (60.47±7.46%)
Rigidity and hypokinesia	49 (76.56±5.30%)	38 (88.37±4.89%)

The main motor disturbances showed similar results in both groups. However, in the group of patients with Parkinson's disease pain syndrome, resting tremor was more pronounced in a higher percentage (87.6%) compared to the group without pain syndrome, confirming that this symptom is mainly associated with motor fluctuations in Parkinson's disease pain syndrome (Table 2)

Methodology. Monitoring of Non-Motor Symptoms: In both groups, the course of non-motor symptoms was analyzed using the questionnaire (NMS Quest). The leading non-motor symptoms in the examined patients were mainly pain, constipation, drowsiness, memory impairment, hyperhidrosis, dry mouth, tachycardia, anxiety, fatigue, paresthesia, and dysfunction of the pelvic organs. Among patients with Parkinson's disease (PD), 60.9% showed anxiety, 56.3% had daytime sleepiness, 70.3% experienced memory loss, 70.3% had hyposmia, 48.4% had generalized hyperhidrosis, 42.2% had orthostatic hypotension, and 45% had salivation. In the group without PD, constipation was observed in 79.1% of patients, 72.1% had depression, 76.7% had memory impairment, and 60.5% had hyposmia. The origin of non-motor symptoms varies depending on the stage of the disease. At Stage I, symptoms include fatigue, pain, anxiety, and tachycardia; at Stage II, fatigue, urinary incontinence, and anxiety are common; at Stage III, constipation, cognitive impairment, and dry mouth are more prevalent. (Non-motor Symptoms Questionnaire (NMSQ)).

Treatment of Non-Motor Symptoms Depending on the Source of Headache: In Stage I, fatigue, nausea, dizziness, tachycardia, and diarrhea were noted; at Stage II, fatigue, urination issues, and anxiety were common; and in Stage III, salivation and cognitive disorders were observed.

Localization of Pain Syndrome: Pain syndrome was observed in 43 patients (35.94±6.0%) in the arm or leg with clearly expressed motor symptoms (hypokinesia and rigidity). In 9 patients (14.1%), pain syndrome was observed on the opposite side. In a quarter of patients, 12 (18.8%) experienced chronic pain bilaterally. Pain syndrome was more pronounced in the proximal upper limb compared to the distal. It was observed in 31 patients (48.44±6.25%) in the proximal upper limb, and in 9 patients (14.06±4.35%) from the first days in the distal part of the hands ($p < 0.001$). Pain in the lumbar region was observed in 23 patients (32.8%). Hip pain was noted in 17 patients (25.1%), knee pain in 12 patients (17.6%), and foot pain in 10 patients (14.7%). Diffuse pain was observed in 21 patients (31%).

Pain in the lumbar region averaged 7.1±0.6 points, headache 5.3±1.1 points, and diffuse pain 6.9±0.7 points. The severity of pain syndrome was 5.1±0.6 points in patients at Stage I, 6.8±0.8 points at Stage II, and 7.5±0.3 points at Stage III (Table 3).

Table 3
Pain Syndrome Intensity at Different Stages of Disease According to the Visual Analog Scale (VAS)

Disease Stage	1-1.5 Stage	2 Stage	2.5-3 Stage
Pain Syndrome Intensity	5.1±0.6	6.8±0.8	7.5±0.3
Akinesia-Rigid Form	7.2±0.9	7.1±1.1	7.2±0.8
Tremor Form	5.3±0.7	5.8±0.6	5.9±0.4
Mixed Form	5.8±0.6	6.4±0.9	6.9±0.9

Pain intensity varied depending on the form of the disease, with higher values in the akinetic-rigid form compared to other forms.

Pain Syndrome Characteristics: Pain in the lumbar region averaged 7.1±0.6 points, headache 5.3±1.1 points, and diffuse pain 6.9±0.7 points. The intensity of pain syndrome was 5.1±0.6 points in patients at Stage I, 6.8±0.8 points at Stage II, and 7.5±0.3 points at Stage III. Pain intensity increased in both men and women as the disease stage progressed.

Pain intensity ranged from 1.7 to 8.3 points on the VAS, averaging 5.5±1.6 points. The maximum discomfort was manifested as muscle spasms and dystonia. According to the McGill Pain Questionnaire, the average score for the sensory-discriminatory and affective-motivational components of pain was 24.4±22.5 (Table 4). The average score on the DN4 neuropathic pain questionnaire was 5.0±2.6 points.

Table 4
McGill Pain Questionnaire Scores

Disease Stage	Pain Intensity (points)	Sensory-Discriminatory Component (points)	Affective-Motivational Component (points)
1-1.5 Stage	2.2	11.3	6.8
2-2.5 Stage	3.6	14.8	4.7
3 Stage	4.5	14.9	7.7

Results and discussion. A total of 64 patients with a diagnosis of pain syndrome related to Parkinson's disease participated in the study. Each patient was divided into groups depending

on the disease stage. This questionnaire not only allowed determining pain intensity but also the sensory and affective components of pain.

To diagnose neuropathic pain, the DN4 questionnaire was used. It is a generalized scale that helps diagnose the development of pathophysiological mechanisms of the pain syndrome, allowing the assessment of both subjective and objective neurological symptoms that change depending on the stage of the disease.

The average score in Part III of the UPDRS scale was 30.9 ± 10.4 points in patients with pain syndrome and 25.5 ± 8.8 points in patients without pain syndrome (Table 3.6). The average score in Part III of the UPDRS scale was higher in patients with pain syndrome, although no significant difference between groups in terms of tremor and rigidity intensity was observed.

Among the 64 patients, 14 (21.9±5.2%) had chronic pain syndrome lasting more than three months. Pain lasting more than one year was observed in 19 patients (29.7±5.7%). Persistent pain was found in 22 patients (34.4±5.9%), and 9 patients (14±4.35%) experienced recurring pain with remissions lasting no more than three months.

Pain Types: In the main group of patients, pain syndrome was mainly associated with bradykinesia, rigidity, tremor, and dystonia. Patients with pain syndrome were evaluated using special pain scales, radiological, laboratory, and neurophysiological tests. The results revealed 5 types of pain syndrome among patients with Parkinson's disease.

1. **Myofascial pain** was found in 23 patients (35.94±6.0%).
2. **Polyneuropathy (neuropathic pain)**, with burning, stabbing pain, and a sensation of "ants crawling," was observed in 19 patients (29.69±5.7%).
3. **Muscle dystonia-related pain** was diagnosed in 12 patients (18.75±4.88%) and manifested as brief spasms lasting several minutes.
4. **Radicular pain** was observed in 6 patients (9.38±3.64%), primarily in the lumbar spine area.
5. **Central (primary) neuropathic pain** was observed in 4 patients (6.25±3.03%) and was considered a result of the direct influence of the disease.

In conclusion, our study differentiated pain into various types. The connection between the pain syndrome and Parkinson's disease was assessed using the following criteria:

1. Pain appeared simultaneously with the onset of the disease or with the worsening of symptoms.
2. Pain is directly related to motor symptoms (is the pain more intense on the side where motor symptoms are more pronounced?).
3. The use of anti-inflammatory drugs leads to pain relief.
4. No other defects are causing the pain.

If patients meet 3 of these criteria and at least one additional criterion, the pain can be linked to Parkinson's disease.

Conclusion: Parkinson's disease with pain syndrome involves both central and peripheral components with the participation of multiple pathophysiological mechanisms. The study identified five different types of pain: myofascial (35.94±6.0%), neuropathic (29.69±5.7%), dystonia-related (18.75±4.88%), radicular (9.38±3.64%), and central (primary) neuropathic pain (6.25±3.03%). Axonopathy and myelinopathy, detected through neurophysiological examinations, are additional causes of the pain syndrome and manifestation of the disease.

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